

APPENDIX E**Example of a recorded conversation**

R: I'm the red one
G: I'm the green one
Y: I'm the yellow one
Y: Has it already started?
G: It hasn't started yet
R: But it looks like the others have already started
R: Sir, has it already started?
EXTERNAL: Not until I say so
R: Hey, we don't start until the teacher says so
R: I'm the red one
G: Yeah, look
G: Look at your screen
ANOTHER: THOSE WHO ARE READY CAN START
G: Can we start?
G: Right, let's get more comfortable.
R: But wait, I can't move
G: I can't move
G: I can't move
G: Weeeeeee
R: How did you jump?
R: Where are you guys?
R: G, G, G how did you jump?
G: No, I fell
G: Wait
G: I don't even care
G: I sound so stupid
Y: I can't get up
Y: How did you jump?
G: Weeee, weeeee. No, I fell again
G: Weeee
G: Uh, there's a big one. I ate it. You didn't eat it.
R: What do I do here?
Y: Is this like a race?
R: Yeah, I don't know what I'm doing
G: Ah, I'm the green one, right? I got stuck.
R: I can't get up
G: Me neither, I got stuck